

CONTEXTUAL CHARACTERISTICS OF VERBS IN THE PHENOMENON OF SEMANTIC MIGRATION

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ANNOTATION

The article talks about the specific features of the verb as a linguistic unit, its important and wide-scale role in expressing thought. The interest in learning the verb is based on a number of factors. Appearing as a lexical unit, a conceptual noun, the verb names certain states, actions or processes occurring in the existence that surrounds us.

Key words: *actant, predicate, valence, presupposition, frame semantics, conceptualization, categorization, prototype.*

The specific characteristics of the verb as a linguistic unit, its important and wide-scale role in the expression of thought have been recognized by linguists many times. The verb has always been of great interest to researchers as it appears as the main unit of expressing knowledge about the world.

The interest in learning the verb is based on a number of factors. Appearing as a lexical unit, a conceptual noun, the verb names certain states, actions or processes occurring in the existence that surrounds us. This or that reality nomination lexically determines the dual role of the verb, since the meaning of the verb not only provides knowledge about a specific reality, but also implies the structure, type, number and general semantic features of this reality. Therefore, the lexical meaning of the verb is very important in the selection of the structure itself, as well as in determining its hidden relations and in the selection of other components of the structure. To show the ability to name a whole situation and to tell its participants, to determine their

status, the verb appears as a predicate. He defines the situation as a single complex whole. In this feature of the verb, its most important role, that is, the need to fill the "void" with certain actants, and thereby realize the syntagmatic potential of the emerging center. The manifestation of a certain type of words as actants implies the predicate character of the verb, determining its syntagmatic arrangement involves different names in the terminology of different authors: "syntagmatic presuppositions" (N.D. Arutyunova), "continuous semantic component" (Yu. .S. Stepanov), "verb choice" (Garnsey S.M.), "valence" (S. D. Katsnelson) or "semantic valence" (L. Tener), "framework" or "frame" (Ch. Fillmore).

Semantically according to the function, with participation in the choice of actants, Ch. Fillmore uses the term "agreement" and calls his semantic-syntactic model the "agreement frame" (It should be noted that the theory proposed by Fillmore as the concept of frame semantics later developed as the theory of agreement grammar). It is in this framework that Ch. According to Fillmore's concept, permanent and facultative clauses can be identified, where they are considered semantically elementary and do not require further subdivision. The meaning of a verb is determined by what agreement relations it can enter into. Many scientists have studied the problems of valence relationships embodied in verbs. The types of syntagmatic communication implied by the valence structure of the verb carry a clear message about the semantics of actants, where it is necessary to admit that there is no mechanism of coexistence. Predictability for a specific verb is largely tied to the mental basis of the valence category. On the basis of this category lies the relationship between the set of relationships consciously organized by man and the meanings of different orders in real existence.

In addition, the speaker of this language must have knowledge of the "morphologically bound syntagmatic potential of the verb" (3, 40-43), and that minimum knowledge is necessary to determine whether or not the next conjunction is possible. The study of valence relations is the main factor in the conceptual analysis of verbs, it is possible to give a complete characterization of the subject and object, to

determine the nature of the effect and its intensity, and to determine possible methods and sources of the effect.

Thus, the uniqueness of the verb as an object of research is recognized by its multifunctionality, its combination as a lexical unit and a predicate unit, and the fact that it contains all the categorical meaning of the sentence. In agreement with many linguists, the verb appears as the grammatical core in the sentence, the center of most syntagmatic devices in it, but it is not always considered the semantic center of the structure. Ideas about the dominant semantic effect of the verb U. It is prominent in the works of Cheif and other representatives of generative semantics. Experts suggest dividing a person's knowledge of the world into two main areas - the verb area and the noun area, U. Cheif recognizes the first of these, that is, the verb, which covers state and reality. According to the scientist, it is the nature of the verb that determines what happens in the rest of the sentence, including what nouns the verb follows and how these nouns relate to it, how these nouns are defined in semantic relations.

Considering the verb as the center of semantic and syntagmatic development, representatives of generative semantics slightly exaggerate the role of the verb in the semantic plan. The verb selects arguments from among the characters, the same situation is observed in the semantic plan. However, structural and semantic plans do not always coincide, implication and text play a huge role in understanding the role of the verb. The study of the verb from the perspective of cognitive linguistics leads to a new interpretation of problems in linguistics, the structure and nature of language, the relationship between semantics and syntax, concept and meaning, problems of polysemy, etc. These problems in linguistics find their adequate solutions within the framework of the theory of cognitive models, conceptualization and categorization, prototypic and frame semantics. The interest in studying the verb is connected with the relativity that appears in its semantics, that is, the meaning with a logical object. The conceptual basis of many verbs is characterized by a wide structure of meaning and the shifting of semantic boundaries, providing the structure and categorization of realities in different ways. The direct participation of the verb in the creation of all

the basic structures of the language leads to consider it as such a basic unit of the language, in which the verb explains various types of categorization of knowledge in its system and describes their general appearance in the language. As mentioned above, the lexical meaning of the verb is a very important factor in determining the syntagmatic structure of the sentence and the structure of its general meaning. The categorical meaning of the verb also plays a very important role in realizing the concrete meaning of the verb lexeme and organizing the structural meaning of the whole sentence.

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